

Building a Scale for Cyberloafing Behavior for High School Teachers in Amman Governorate

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to build and apply a scale for cyberloafing behavior for high school teachers at Amman governorate; the study sample consisted of (609) male and female teachers. To achieve the study objective, a scale for cyberloafing was developed, consisting of (45) items in its final shape; the scale's validity and reliability were verified. The study results revealed a moderate level of cyberloafing for the study sample; also, the study results showed no statistically significant differences between the means of cyberloafing behavior attributed to teacher's gender; the study recommends some recommendations, the most prominent was exploring the level of cyberloafing behavior for high school students.

1. Introduction

The current age is the era of the knowledge explosion, the digital revolution, and rapid and successive changes in all fields. One of the secretions of this era is the development in the fields of communications and information technology, as social networks have become a popular and successful success among members of one society, and have extended to link human relations between the countries of the world, its continents and countries. The world became a small village that one can roam across its continents and countries by controlling some buttons on the keyboard of a computer or mobile device.

The age of knowledge and information is named for those societies that are characterized by the use of science and knowledge for progress and advancement, which always seeks social change. Many industries and investments have become dependent on knowledge, information, technology and an economy based on knowledge and information that is growing with a percentage greater than the economy that builds on the implementation of orders only three times; it can be said that the era of knowledge and information is the age that controls the country's economy from exports and imports (Kim and Byrne, 2011).

The World Wide Web has witnessed a remarkable development in recent years, not only to achieve communication but also to become a major tool in the educational process, and new and evolving patterns of tools for the web emerged more interactively and participative, which led to the entry of the web in an advanced stage of development called social media sites, it managed with all the advantages it provided to attract large numbers of users, as the user has become a producer of the information and not a consumer of it, and social networks are among the most significant phenomena in the current era as the feature of the era that is attributed to many uses seen today, and with its platforms that are not limited to it allows monitoring, tracking, and interactive exchange between subscribers, which means it is an excellent way to use in marketing products and services (Richard, 2012).

Social networking sites began to appear in the late nineties (Classmates.com) in (1995) when used to connect colleagues. A group of social networks appeared between the years (1999-2001), but it could not continue, as the true birth of social communication networks as we know it today in (2002), before the term "Social Media Sites" appeared, there was the so-called Web 1.0 and Web 1.5 (web 1.0 and web1.5) where most features of the web 1.0 (web1.0) that it consisted of (Html) consistent pages. It was only updated rarely, then came web 1.5 (web1.5), which is a dynamic web in which Internet pages are created quickly through the contents of the databases used in managing pages. After that, social media sites appeared that were not limited to being pages A dynamic web, with broader and more extensive use of the multimedia, by providing images, videos, sound clips, blogs, and more (WooSwearer, Wang, Maag, Siebecker, & Frerichs, 2012).

With the emergence of the Friendster site, this achieves excellent success at the time. In the second half of the same year, the Skyrock network appeared in France as a platform for blogging, and at the beginning of

the year (2005), the American MySpace website appeared. The number of its views exceeded Google at the time, and it is considered one of the first and largest social networks in the world, and it is in Great competition with Facebook (FaceBook), which started to spread in parallel with MySpace, but enjoyed large numbers of users worldwide (Wang, & Nansel, 2009).

The development of information technology and the Internet is the most important change that led to the information age, and in the information age, internet technologies have become part of personal and business life. They have brought great benefits to users, and alongside the advantages of information technology, some threats of misuse have emerged. One of the most existing cases is the online staff hangout In the workplace, which causes many institutions' problems. Because of the expansion of local networks and the global Internet, the computer cannot be excluded from work, so cyberloafing is a common fact in institutions today, as companies have high-speed access channels to the Internet and workers can use it (Özler and Polat, 2012) (Kim and Byrne, 2011).

Cyberloafing behavior by workers contributes to evading their job duties and the ease of obtaining various information technology devices such as (laptops, tablets, and smartphones) as well as widespread internet services, all of which contributed to enabling workers to use these devices for personal purposes during Business hours (Lim and Don, 2012).

Cyberloafing refers to employees' use of the Internet during their official working hours for personal purposes, and cyberloafing includes many examples including browsing websites for personal and non-work-related purposes such as social networks, sports, news, entertainment, checking email and sending personal messages, and other activities such as Online shopping and online games (Vitak, Crouse, and LaRose, 2011).

It has been observed that blogging and instant messaging are the most common activities, which leads to the depletion of working hours. Online gambling, personal investment, and online auctions are troubling forms of electronic loitering, and electronic loitering has become the most common method for employees to get rid of working hours. Unlike previous times, Internet access has become easy today for working individuals. Hence, their tendency to use the Internet enables them to relax from work stress, so electronic loitering is a form of psychological withdrawal behavior (Madden, 2009).

Types of cyberloafing

Cyberloafing behavior has been classified into harmful cyberloafing such as: viewing adult sites, playing online games, and the use of unprotected areas, which can cause harm to the institution in which it operates, and secondary cyberloafing includes: Online shopping, personal email follow-up, or an electronic tutorial through activity on different professional pages or groups, lack of self-control plays a significant role in the practice of cyberloafing and the inability to stop or control it. The process of self-control and control of personal reactions to everything that happens are the most influential factors on the ability of the individual to absorb the behaviors of society around them, and to deal positively with it, in light of the different attitudes and thinking of each individual in this society or at work, and thus his ability to control the effects of different events (Ahmad and Omar, 2017).

Banerjee and Thankur (2016) point out that cyberloafing behavior depends not only on the psychological factor but also on the work environment, the employee's personal needs, and job satisfaction. The better the work environment and the greater the job satisfaction of employees, the less they practice cyberloafing.

Cyberloafing is classified into two types: non-dangerous cyberloafing and involves receiving and sending personal emails at work; serious cyberloafing, including online gaming, visiting adult websites, gambling online, and visiting unsafe sites can cause damage to the organization (Blanchard and Henle, 2008).

Effects of cyberloafing

Some researchers assume that cyberloafing is a lost activity and results in empty labor. In contrast, others believe that cyberloafing during working hours is necessary and has positive effects; the following is a presentation of the positive and negative results of cyberloafing.

Positive effects of cyberloafing

The practice of cyberloafing for a short period in non-work tasks has some benefits, including reducing stress, boredom, which leads to renewal, improving the employee's mental state, which leads to greater satisfaction and greater creativity for employees. Informal web browsing can also help develop skills that can be used by institutions in recreational activities when employees can complete a reasonable amount of personal activities during working hours (Blanchard and Henle, 2008; Vitak et al., 2011).

People engaged in recurring Internet activities during business hours tend to have more job satisfaction than less frequent users. Some studies such as (Stoddart (2016) and Ghani, Muslim, and Rasli, 2018) have also indicated, allowing employees during working hours to use the Internet can increase commitment to the organization as they can better balance their work and private lives and recreational use of the Internet for fun, play. Online shopping can renew employees' energy and reduce their anxiety and stress (Ovarec, 2002).

Negative effects of cyberloafing

Cyberloafing can lead to a significant reduction in productivity in organizations and companies and other adverse effects if an employee engages in any illegal activity on the Internet that threatens company information such as spyware and malware, and sexual harassment and security threats and away from performing the required tasks leading to low productivity and losing time (Lim, 2002; and Bock et al., 2010).

Askew, 2012, argues that cyberloafing may be a form of psychological withdrawal, as it acts as a typical withdrawal behavior, (Fisher 2004) argues that cyberloafing is a measure that provides a mental escape from the working environment and gives the employee a sense of comfort and relaxation. Some studies have shown that some forms of cyberloafing are acceptable at work and that social navigation on social sites has a positive impact on employees, email follow-up harms staff feelings. Studies have shown that men are more susceptible to cyberloafing than females.

Previous studies:

The following is an overview of the previous studies reached and related to the subject of study.

Lim and Chen (2012) conducted a study to identify the effects of cyberloafing on staff feelings and work in Singapore. The study sample consisted of (500) male and female employees. The study results showed that in general, employees do not mind practicing a simple cyberloafing; the results also showed that males indicated positive effects of cyberloafing on work, the results also showed that males are more practicing cyberloafing compared to females.

A study conducted by (Ghani, Muslim, and Rasli, 2018) identified the nature of the relationship between work pressure and cyberloafing behavior among a sample of Malaysian government employees consisting of (120) employees; the questionnaire was used as a study tool. The study results showed that there is a positive correlation statistically significant between the level of work pressure and behavior of cyberloafing and that the work pressure affects employees so that they tend to the behavior of cyberloafing.

Yildirim and Varol (2018) conducted a study aimed at detecting the level of practice of cyberloafing behavior in the classroom from students' perspective; the sample of the study consisted of (228) university students in Turkey. The study results showed that the type of communication used by the teacher in the lecture hall and the teaching strategies used by him lead students to practice the behavior of cyberloafing.

Stoddart (2016) conducted a study aimed at identifying cyberloafing and mental alertness and their impact on psychological combustion; the study consisted of (219) employees, (124) males and (94) females. The study results showed an average level of mental alertness, a low level of cyberloafing in the study sample, and the results indicated the practice of cyberloafing and mental alertness reduce the psychological burning of employees.

Naranjua, Akinci, Lemon, and Togol conducted a study to identify the perceptions of secondary school teachers in Turkey on strategies for managing impression and cyberloafing. The study sample consisted of (316) teachers; the results of the study showed that the level of teachers' practice of cyberloafing behavior was moderate and found a positive correlation statistically significant between impression management strategies and cyberloafing.

Cinar and Karcioğlu (2015) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between cybercrime behavior and organizational citizenship behavior in Erzurum, Turkey. The sample consisted of (360) government employees. The questionnaire was used to collect data from the study sample. The results showed that the level of cyberloafing in the study sample was average, organizational citizenship behavior was high, and the study showed no correlation between cyberloafing behavior and organizational citizenship behavior.

Yasar and Yurdugul (2013) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between electronic activities and the practice of cyberloafing behavior among students in Turkish universities. The sample of the study consisted of (215) male and female students. The study results showed a significant correlation between the "addiction behavior" dimension and the tendency to practice the behavior of cyberloafing.

Varghese & Barber (2017) conducted a study to discover the intermediate influence of the role of stress on the relationship between the five personality types and the practice of cyberloafing behavior. The study sample consisted of (343) employees from different job sites in the United States, the results of the study showed that the personal elements (diastolic) and (neurotic) and (role disorder) were positively associated with the behavior of cyberloafing. Regression analysis showed that (role disturbance) is a predictor of the behavior of cyberloafing, and that the element (conscience) and (approval) was negatively correlated with the degree of exercise of cyberloafing behavior.

Heidari (2018) conducted a study to investigate the effect of cyberloafing on the sense of happiness and academic integration of medical students at the University of Shiraz in Iran. The study sample consisted of (195) male and female students. The study results showed that cyberloafing has a negative and statistically significant effect on students' academic integration and happiness. The results showed a positive correlation between the sense of happiness and academic integration.

(Saleh, Daqqa, Abdul Rahim, and Sakallah, 2018) conducted a study in Saudi Arabia aimed at investigating the effect of cyberloafing on employee productivity. The study results showed that the study sample consisted of (250) employees from (20) companies. The use of the Internet for one hour and educational purposes increases

the employee productivity level threefold. The study results also showed that blocking access to social networking sites and browsing the web leads to increased employee productivity and increased learning activities through the Internet.

Comment on previous studies

It is noted from the review of previous studies that they differed in terms of the sample used. The sample of some consists of employees, others are students, and they varied in their places of study; some of them were conducted in the United States and others in Turkey, Iran. It is noted through the review of previous studies the extent of researchers interest in this behavior and the associated effects (Varghese & Barber, 2017) study sought to examine the relationship between the practice of lounging behavior and the five factors of personality. As for the study of Heidari (2018) sought to know the impact of cyberloafing on the feeling of happiness and academic integration among students of the Faculty of Medicine, this study differs from other previous studies in terms of its endeavor to build a measure of cyberloafing for teachers in the Jordanian environment and determine the nature of this behavior. What are the most prominent of these practices? It is the first study within the limits of the researcher's knowledge, which is conducted on teachers of public secondary schools in Jordan.

Study Questions

This study tried to answer the following questions:

The first question: What are the implications of the validity of the scale of cyberloafing behavior among high school teachers in Al Jamiaa' Directorate of Education?

The second question: What is the significance of the reliability of the scale of cyberloafing behavior among high school teachers in Al Jamiaa' Directorate of Education?

The fourth question: Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the arithmetic mean of cyberloafing behavior by gender.

The importance of the study

This theoretical study's importance is: In addressing one of the important research topics in cognitive psychology, educational psychology, and learning strategies, which is cyberloafing, this study also draws the attention of educators and parents on the need to pay attention to this topic.

This study's practical significance is: To draw the attention of researchers and interested in the cyberloafing scale, which has appropriate psychometric properties, for use in similar studies.

The terminology of the study and procedural definitions

Social Media Sites:

It is a group of electronic networks globally spread through the Internet, and it allows subscribers to create their site while ensuring that it can be linked to other sites and other members with the same interests, interests, and hobbies.

The present study means A collection of apps available on the Internet such as blogs, YouTube, Wiki, Facebook, Twitter, Myspace, and Google Plus, which enables students to use it and reveal student responses to the study tool measure the degree of lounging and this.

Study Limits and Limitations

The following limits determine the study:

Human limitations: The study was applied to a sample of secondary school teachers in public schools.

Time limits: The study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year (2018-2019).

Spatial limits: Al Jamiaa' Directorate of Education

Study Limitations: The study was limited to the tools used, the methodology used. Therefore, the validity of the study's findings is determined by the tools' validity and reliability and the validity of the methods used in this study.

The generalization of this study's results is determined by the appropriateness, reliability, and reliability of the instruments used.

Terms and Procedural Definitions:

Cyberloafing

Lim (2002) defined it as such acts in which employees exploit Internet connectivity through their organizations or smartphones for personal purposes, such as browsing social networking sites, sports, reading news, and entertainment, sending and receiving personal emails, and some other activities such as shopping or playing games online.

This study defines procedurally as the degree obtained by the respondent on the cyberloafing scale, which was prepared in this study.

Method and Procedures

Study Methodology: This study used the descriptive analytical approach, being the most suitable for the study's nature.

Study population

The study population consisted of all 4390 male and female secondary school teachers, according to the statistics of the Planning and Formations Department in the Directorate for the year 2017-2018, the first chapter.

Study sample

The sample of the study included (609) male and female teachers selected by simple random method.

Study tools

Cyberloafing scale

To answer the study questions, a cyberloafing scale was prepared. Previous studies and similar measurement tools were introduced like Haidari (2018) and Ghani, Muslim and Rasli (2018) study, then the objectives of the scale were determined in accordance with the global trends and trends in detecting the problems of cyberloafing, they also met with some teachers and asked them to answer the operations and sites they are browsing when they enter social media sites and open their devices in general during working hours, later, a group of paragraphs was constructed for the scale in its initial form of (56) items, after the completion of the test construction it was Presented to six arbitrators and experts from faculty, teachers, educational supervisors and principals, they were asked to give their opinion on: language integrity, accuracy of wording, clarity of paragraphs, relevance to the subject of study, and adding and deleting what they deem appropriate, and their observations were followed, and (5) items were unanimously agreed by the arbitrators to delete, the scale was applied to a survey sample consisting of (50) male and female teachers in order to identify the clarity of the paragraphs of the scale and to ensure the validity and reliability of the test, determine the time needed to answer the scale, and based on the results of the survey sample, the test was finalized and consisted of (45) items.

The scale's initial picture was applied to a group of teachers (20) male and female teachers from outside the basic study sample. The researchers explained to them the importance of answering seriously and to express their opinion about each paragraph of the scale in case it was not understood or unclear; their observations were then collected, and their responses emptied, and in the light of these findings, some paragraphs were revised to become more evident.

Scale reliability

To check the stability of the scale, it was applied to a survey sample consisting of (50) teachers outside the study sample. Two weeks later, the correlation coefficient between the two applications was calculated at 0.83. It is suitable for the present study, and the internal consistency of Cronbach Alfa was calculated as 0.89.

Verification of the normal distribution of the response of the study members

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used, and it has a value of (0.160) and a level of significance (0.080), which indicates that the response of the study sample on the scale is distributed naturally.

Correction of the study tool

The five-point grading was used in the study tool as follows: To a very large degree and given (5) degrees, Significantly (4) degrees, moderate degree (3) degrees, a small degree (2) degree, very few degrees (1) degree, and the levels of cyberloafing were judged by the following equation: (Highest value in staging - lowest value) / 3

$$(5-1)/3 = 1.33$$

Thus categories are as follows:

From (1- 2.33) low.

(2.34 - 3.67) Average.

(3.68 - 5) High

Statistical treatment

The following statistical treatments were used:

Arithmetic means and standard deviations

Correlation coefficients

Study Results

First-class exploratory analysis using orthogonal axes

Standard error method In measurement: The standard error is used as an indicator of stability.

The first question: What are the indications of the cyberloafing scale's validity among high school teachers in the university brigade?

To answer this question, construction validity indicators were extracted, any correlation of paragraphs with the total score and table (1) shows that.

First: Construction validity

Construction validity indicators were verified by finding the correlation of paragraphs with the scale's overall score, and Table 1 shows this.

Table 1: The value of the correlation coefficients of the paragraphs with the total score of the scale

Paragraph number	Correlation coefficient	Paragraph number	Correlation coefficient	Paragraph number	Correlation coefficient
1	0.52**	16	**0.62	31	**0.48
2	0.51**	17	**0.71	32	**0.57
3	0.61**	18	**0.48	33	**0.39
4	0.45**	19	**0.47	34	**0.61
5	0.50**	20	**0.51	35	**0.46
6	**0.49	21	**0.42	36	**0.56
7	**0.52	22	0.46**	37	**0.49
8	0.46**	23	**0.46	38	**0.63
9	**0.45	24	**0.68	39	**0.61
10	**0.62	25	0.52**	40	**0.57
11	**0.43	26	0.51**	41	**0.63
12	0.42**	27	0.61**	42	**0.40
13	**0.49	28	0.45**	43	**0.47
14	**0.60	29	0.55**	44	**0.56
15	0.52**	30	**0.64	45	**0.54

**significant at ($\alpha = 0.01$)

Notes from the results of table (1) that the values of correlation coefficients were all positive and more than (0.30) and statistically function at the level ($\alpha = 0.01$).

Second: Honesty factor: The validity of the global scale was verified by conducting exploratory factor analysis from first class on the sample as a whole using the Principal Component analysis for individual responses to test paragraphs, recycling was performed using Varimax Rotation for factors whose latent root values were more significant than (1), for each factor from explained variance and eigenvalues and the root values of the elements were calculated, Table 2 shows these results.

Table 2: The values of the Latent root and the ratio of explained variance and cumulative rate for factors of cyberloafing scale

Factors	Latent root	Interpreted contrast ratio%	Interpreted cumulative contrast ratio
1	18.754	41.675	41.675
2	2.697	5.993	47.668
3	1.076	2.390	50.059
4	1.051	2.336	52.395

The results of table (2) show that there are only four factors whose Latent root values are more significant than (1) and interpreted the percentage of (52.395) of the total variation in performance on the cyberloafing scale, and the value of the underlying root of the first factor was (18,754) and explained (41.675%) of the variation in performance on the lounge scale, the underlying root value of the second factor was (2.687) and explained (5.993%) of the variance on the scale, it is noted from the results of table (1) that the ratio of the latent root of the first factor to the latent root of the second factor is equal to (6.953) it is greater than (2)

This means a one-dimensional check for the attribute measured by the cyberloafing meter, and the following figure shows the graphical representation of the Scree Plot values of the Latent root of the dimensions of the test.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of the factors constituent of the cyberloafing scale.

Figure (1) shows the factors with Latent root that explain the variation in performance on the cyberloafing scale, noting that the value of the underlying root of the first factor is large compared to that of the second latent root, while noting a shift in the slope of the curve at the second factor which indicates the presence of a dominant factor can be inferred from it on the availability of a one-dimensional property in performance on this scale.

The second question: What is the significance of the reliability of the scale of cyberloafing behavior among high school teachers in Al Jamiaa' Directorate of Education?
Reliability coefficients were verified in the following ways:

First: Internal consistency using the Alpha Cronbach equation.

It was extracted on the primary sample (N = 609). Its value was (0.901), which is high and suitable for the present study.

Second: Split-half Reliability.

Its value was (0.89), which is considered suitable for the present study.

The standard error in scale

The standard error of the scale is found for the whole score where the standard error is used as an indicator of reliability; it has a value of (0.008), which indicates a high and suitable stability coefficient.

Question 3: What is the significance of the reliability of the scale of cyberloafing behavior among high school teachers in Al Jamiaa' Directorate of Education?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the sections of the cyberloafing scale were extracted, and table (3) shows that.

Table 3: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the level of cyberloafing for high school teachers

Paragraph number	Paragraph	Arithmetic average	Standard deviation	Rank	Level
38	I always check the battery charge of my cell phone	4.35	1.31	1	
27	Angered when I had to get out of what I was following on the Web	4.11	1.47	2	High
10	I check personal emails within working hours.	4.10	0.77	3	High
29	I prefer browsing my phone to share works	4.04	1.07	4	High
43	I guess I can't shut down my phone during business hours	3.97	1.07	5	High
1	I browse websites during working hours.	3.94	1.15	6	High
32	I have accumulated a lot of tasks because of preoccupation with a telephone during working hours	3.93	1.27	7	High

15	I reply to messages that I receive via WhatsApp	3.92	1.42	8	High
7	I shop online at work hours	3.87	1.40	9	High
40	When students take the tests, I hang out online via my smartphone	3.84	1.38	10	High
26	I feel like I'm in another environment	3.81	1.14	11	High
45	Having WIFI at school is a beautiful thing	3.75	1.23	12	High
4	I browse entertainment sites during working hours.	3.73	1.36	13	High
20	Priority is sometimes given to browsing websites at the expense of work	3.70	1.40	14	Average
24	Time passes quickly when I use social media	3.65	1.36	15	Average
41	Most colleagues get busy with their phones during working hours	3.65	1.84	16	Average
31	My social contact with my colleagues is less because of the smartphone	3.59	1.09	17	Average
14	It is difficult for me to complete the work without opening my phone	3.57	1.29	18	Average
5	Browse investment-related websites. Not connected to work.	3.56	1.45	19	Average
11	I send personal emails within working hours.	3.56	1.17	20	Average
8	I forget the tasks required of me because of preoccupation with online	3.55	1.60	21	Average
18	I follow videos on YouTube	3.51	1.41	22	Average
6	Browse sports sites, which are not connected to work during working hours.	3.50	1.58	23	Average
12	I communicate with my friends on social media during work	3.47	1.50	24	Average
13	I can't work without my phone	3.43	1.62	25	Average
42	The school director tries to alleviate this phenomenon	3.43	1.72	26	Average
34	I feel I cannot leave the social networking sites.	3.42	1.67	27	Average
2	I browse public news sites during working hours.	3.40	1.59	28	Average
21	Use websites when I don't have work pressure	3.40	1.51	29	Average
39	I rarely communicate with my colleagues because I am busy with the phone	3.39	1.68	30	Average
9	I receive email messages that are non-work-related,	3.36	1.61	31	Average
28	I am late going to my class because I am busy browsing social media	3.32	1.10	32	Average
35	I feel psychological exhaustion due to attachment to the phone	3.27	0.72	33	Average
23	I browse websites through the class	3.21	1.93	34	Average
19	I feel like I'm wasting work time	3.20	1.72	35	Average
16	I watch videos that I receive via WhatsApp	3.20	1.37	36	Average
17	I am careful to follow WhatsApp	3.19	1.41	37	Average
22	I believe that the use of networking sites during working hours keeps me up to date with events in the world	3.14	1.31	38	Average
25	I think using these sites will drain my effort and energy	2.89	1.71	39	Average
30	I always feel there is something I will miss if I don't open my phone	2.71	1.78	40	Average
37	I check my phone periodically	2.68	1.54	41	Average
36	I suffer from confusion and lack of focus in my	2.65	1.34	42	Average

work due to cyberloafing						
44	Cyberloafing makes me not feel the passage of time	2.61	1.70	43	Average	
3	I download non-work-related information during working hours.	2.33	1.66	44	Weak	
33	It would be preferable if smartphones are dispensed	2.30	1.43			Weak
Total marks		3.46	0.92	Average		

It is noted from the results of table (3) that the level of cyberloafing among the sample of the study was average, the mean was 3.46 with a standard deviation of 0.92, and that the arithmetic averages came in the high, medium, and low levels ranging between (4.35 -2.30). Paragraph 38 came first. Which says, "I check the battery charge of my cell phone constantly" With an arithmetic mean (4.35) and a standard deviation (1.31), in the last rank came paragraph (33), Which states that "It would be preferable if smartphones are dispensed" with arithmetic mean (2.30) and standard deviation (1.43) and low level.

Fourth question: Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the arithmetic mean of cyberloafing behavior by gender.

To answer this question, arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and T-test of two independent samples were extracted. Table (4) shows that.

Table 4:Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and T-test of two independent samples of the level of cyberloafing by gender

Gender	number	Arithmetic average	standard deviation	T		
Cyberloafing	Males	243	3.50	0.91	1.186	0.236
	Females	366	3.41	0.93		

It is noted from the results of table (4) that there are no statistically significant differences between the mean averages of the level of cyberloafing by gender. As the value of "T" is(1.186), where it is not statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.05$), this result can be attributed to the fact that both males and females practice cyberloafing at the same frequency. The results of the answer to this question are relatively consistent with the results of a study (Cinar and Karcioğlu, 2015) which indicated an average level of cyberloafing in the study sample, where the answers to this question differed from the results of the study (Lim and Chen, 2012) where its results showed that males are more practicing cyberloafing than females. It also disagreed with the findings of (Stoddart 2016) study, where its results indicated a low level of cyberloafing.

Recommendations

The researchers come up with some recommendations.

1. There is a possibility of adopting the education and the teachings of this training program and making a plan to apply it to school teachers and administrative staff of the Ministry to empower school teachers and train them in human performance technology skills to improve performance and achieve goals.
2. Conducting more studies and research on this critical topic and discussing its link with other variables and developing training programs in education at the university and institute level.
3. There is keenness of the training departments in the directorates of education to research human performance technology, follow up on recent studies in it, and the educational supervisors' familiarity with the implications of this new approach.

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